

TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CRITICAL THINKING IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Annotation. *This article covers issues of the development of critical thinking in the primary education system, methods of applying critical development technologies, forms and principles of the development of critical thinking, actions for the formation of critical thinking, stages and activities of critical thinking of students, methods called "Correct statements" and "Monitoring Journal".*

Key words: *critical thinking, principles, scientific literacy, technology, personal qualities, knowledge, skills, information, methods of "correct statements" and "Monitoring Journal".*

ТЕХНОЛОГИИ РАЗВИТИЯ КРИТИЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ У МЛАДШИХ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ

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Аннотация. *В данной статье освещаются вопросы развития критического мышления в системе начального образования, методы применения технологий критического развития, формы и принципы развития критического мышления, действия по формированию критического мышления, этапы и деятельность критического мышления учащихся, методы "правильных утверждений" и "журнал мониторинга".*

Ключевые слова: *критическое мышление, принципы, научная грамотность, технологии, личностные качества, знания, навыки, информация, методы "правильных утверждений" и "журнал мониторинга".*

The introduction of the technology for the development of critical thinking in the current 21st century primary education system has become an urgent topic the main reason for this is due to the researchers' views on the possibility of the formation of critical thinking [1].

Critical thinking is the ability of an individual to overcome a specific tendency to dogmatic perception, to analyze one or another problem, to use it. Information from

various sources that distinguish objective reality is subjective opinion about it, logical conclusion assumptions or prejudice in various biases, the ability of a person to adequately identify, the causes and conditions of problems in his life, readiness to act are signified by their practical (not only rhetorical) resolution.

The technology for the development of critical thinking can also be included as methods of educating a modern active personality [3]. The application of critical development technology is understood as the contribution to the formation of thinking and speech abilities of students in the lessons of thinking, in particular, natural sciences, the development of primary classes, their creative abilities, skills, awareness of the laws of nature, observation, clear and logical work, working with statements about the goals and specific state of scientific literacy competence.

The technology of “correct statements” developed in the research process is recommended.

The teacher explains to students how to work with “ correct and incorrect statements "or"correct" technology. Students choose "correct statements" from those proposed by the teacher.

The" correct " technique can be used at different stages of the lesson:

- knowledge update;
- work on new material;
- show, reflect.

Instructions for using this technology:

- on your table there is a table that you need to fill. The numbers in the table indicate the question numbers.

- I am reading you a question, if you believe, that is, if the answer is correct, put " + "on the second line, if you do not believe– you will put the sign"–".

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

If this technology was used before studying a new topic, then after studying the information, you need to return to the table and assess the correctness of the assumptions, reliability in the third row.

The next reception is called "Monitoring Journal". On-board magazines are a generalizing name for various methods of educational writing, according to which students write their thoughts while studying the topic. In the simplest way, readers write the answers to the following questions in a journal:

Monotoring magazine

What do I know about this topic?	What did I learn in the lesson?	What did I not understand in the lesson?

The importance of this technology is that it teaches children to listen and hear, develops speech, gives the opportunity to communicate, activates mental activity, cognitive interest, encourages children to act, so everyone works. Fear disappears, the responsibility of the student for his response increases, the teacher and students participate together in the acquisition of knowledge.

Learning to think critically is not an easy task. There is no list of steps that lead to critical thinking [4]. But according to the authors of the technology, there are certain conditions and approaches that develop critical thinking (Figure 1):

Thus, students who think critically, are involved in the active process of systematic work, think about their knowledge, are able to assert themselves and

Figure 1. Conditions and approaches that develop critical thinking

In theory, everything is simple and in practice there are certain difficulties::
- they can correctly understand themselves in the world around them.

- the teacher must resume all work in the lessons, spend more time preparing;
- no ready-made methodological developments;
- technology is not used in every lesson [5]. Not all children are able to work with a lot of information. The reading technique is not the same for everyone, not everyone can work synchronously. Technology is not always effective in low-absorbing classes (like any other development).

At the same time, a huge field of activity is opened for the creative work of teachers and students.

Therefore, it is important to know everyone and involve themselves in the process of self-knowledge. But I am sure that over time, most of the problems will be solved, since this technology – the technology for the development of critical thinking through reading and writing – is becoming more and more widespread, and then the opportunity to educate a future citizen, an independent, creative person, will increase over time.

Summarizing all of the above, we can say that the "technology for the development of critical thinking" and its main strategies provide for the development of thinking, scientific literacy and the formation of creative abilities. This technology meets the educational goals at the present stage, equipping the student and teacher with methods of working with information, methods of organizing the teaching of self-education.

The reason is, the sensations that arise under the influence of this being are realized in many ways not by him himself, but through how we perceive and imagine. In place of the conclusion, it can be said that virtual existence is currently used in the sphere and branches of human cultural activity [6].

In place of the conclusion, it can be said that a developed culture of thinking allows you to contribute to the appearance. The dynamic development of a new, independent-minded generation leads to the need for constant work on oneself, strengthening in society.

The responsibility of each person for his future, this is exactly what the system of development of critical thinking helps. Given that important foundations are formed in the elementary grades of personality development, we consider it necessary to start forming. Critical thinking from primary school age, the study of the practice of organizing educational activities at the primary stage indicates an insufficient level of School critical development. For elementary students, this is not enough, as the ability to independently acquire knowledge, mental operations allow you to develop the ability to move from accuracy to abstract, conclusions, comparisons, hypothetical judgments.

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